

BEDA URIG'INI QURITKICHGA YUKLASH - TEKISLASH JARANINING MATEMATIK MODELINI TAVSIFI.

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Annotatsiya: maqolada beda urig'ini quritgich konveyeriga yuklash - tekislash jarayonini matematik modelning kanonik o'zgarishlari natijalari berilgan Tenglamani kanonik ravishda o'zgartirganda, kelib chiqishi yangi nuqtaga ko'chiriladi va eski o'qlarni factor fazosida ma'lum burchakka buriladi, natijada chiziqli hadlari yo'qoladi va erkin hadlarning qiymati o'zgaradi.

Topilgan koeffitsiyentlar bo'yicha ikkinchi darajali regressiya tenglamasi tuzilgan. Differensial tenglamalar sistemasini yechish orqali yangi markazning koordinatalarini topamiz. Regressiya koeffitsientlarini kanonik shaklda aniqlash uchun xarakterlovchi tenglama yechildi. Hisoblar natijasida regressiya koeffitsientlarining qiymatlari olinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: optimal, topish, aniqlash ko'rsatkich, notekislik, yuklash, tekislash, beda urig'i, materialni etkazib berish tezligi, quritgich, konveyer, tajriba, omil, rejalashtirish matritsasi, mezon, regressiya koeffitsienti, optimallashtirish parametri, gipoteza, adekvatlik, tajriba xatolari, dispersiya, statistik baholash.

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Kirish

Bir nechta omillar ishtirok etadigan va o'zaro ta'sir qiladigan murakkab jarayonlarni o'rganayotganda, ularni optimallashtirish vazifasi ko'p faktorli bo'lib, uning echimini eksperimentni rejalashtirishning maxsus usullarini qo'llash va ikkinchi darajali regressiya tenglamasi bilan o'rganiladi. Bir xil bo'lmagan sharoitida optimal sohani tavsiflash uchun tadqiqot ob'ektining matematik modelini olish uchun Boks va Benkin tomonidan rotatabelli uch darajali plan ishlab chiqilgan.

Eksperiment markazi aniqlanadigan funktsiyaning optimal qiymatiga yaqinroq bo'lgan yangi nuqtada tik ko'tarilish dasturini amalga oshirishni hisobga olgan holda tanlangan.

Metod

Optimal maydonni tavsiflab, etarli ikkinchi darajali matematik modelni olgandan so'ng, parametrining optimal qiymatiga mos keladigan nuqtaning koordinatalarini aniqlash va uning atrofidagi aniqlanadigan yuzasining xususiyatlarini o'rganish kerak.

Topilgan koeffitsiyentlar bo'yicha ikkinchi darajali regressiya tenglamasi tuzildi

$$Y = 10,833 - 2,3625 X_4 + 3,175 X_5 + 3,2375 X_8 + 0,075 X_4 X_5 + 0,05 X_4 X_8 - 0,825 X_5 X_6 + 0,4085 X_4^2 + 1,7835 X_5^2 \quad (1)$$

Qo'zg'almas mintaqada aniqlanadigan yuzasining xususiyatini o'rganish uchun regressiya tenglamasi (1) ni kanonik shakliga o'tkaziladi

$$Y = Y_s B_{11} X_1^2 + B_{22} X_2^2 + B_{33} X_3^2 \quad (2)$$

bu erda Y - optimallashtirish mezonining qiymati;

U_s - optimal nuqtada optimallashtirish mezonining qiymati;

X_i - yangi koordinata o'qlari;

B_{ii} - kanonik shaklda regressiya koeffitsientlari.

Tenglamani kanonik ravishda o'zgartirganda, koordinatani boshlanishi yangi nuqta S ga ko'shiriladi va eski o'qlarni omil fazosida ma'lum bir burchakka burish natijasida chiziqli hadlar yo'qoladi, erkin hadlarining qiymati o'zgaradi.

Differensial tenglamalar sistemasini yechish orqali yangi markazning koordinatalarini topdik

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dY}{dX_4} = -2,3625 + 0,075X_5 + 0,05X_8 + 0,817X_4 = 0 \\ \frac{dY}{dX_5} = 3,175 + 0,075X_4 - 0,825X_8 + 3,567X_5 = 0 \\ \frac{dY}{dX_8} = 3,2375 + 0,05X_4 - 0,825X_5 + 3,717X_8 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

va (1) tenglamani yechib, unga olingan omillar qiymatlarini qo'yeib $S(Y_S)$ nuqtada optimallashtirish parametrining qiymati aniqlandi.

Regressiya koeffitsientlarini kanonik shaklda aniqlash uchun xarakteristik tenglama echildi

$$f_{(6)} = \begin{vmatrix} 0,4085 - B & 0,0375 & 0,025 \\ 0,0375 & 1,7835 - B & -0,4125 \\ 0,025 & -0,4125 & 1,8585 - B \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (4)$$

(4) tenglamani echish kompyuterda amalga oshirildi. Hisob-kitoblar natijasida koeffitsientlarni quyidagi qiymatlari olinadi:

$$B_{44} = 0,40428; B_{55} = 1,42699; B_{88} = 2,21873.$$

Kanonik ko'rinishdagi regressiya tenglamasi (1) quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi

$$Y - 3,329 = 0,40428X_4^2 + 1,42699X_5^2 + 2,21873X_8^2 \quad (5)$$

Kvadratik tenglamadagi barcha koeffitsientlar ijobiy qiymatlarga ega bo'lganligi sababli, (1) tenglama bilan tavsiflangan yuzasi sirt markazining koordinatalari bo'lgan uch o'lchovli paraboloiddir: $X_{4S} = 3,0770$; $X_{5S} = 1,2289$; $X_{8S} = 1,1852$ (omillar mos ravishda quyidagi qiymatlarga ega: baraban aylanishlar chastotasi – 45,4 rad/s, materialni uzatish tezligi – 7,4.10-3 m/s, material qatlamining balandligi – 0,78 m). Shunday qilib, figura markazi tajriba maydoni va aprior tanlangan tajriba markazi yaqinida joylashganligi aniqlandi.

Xulosa

Tahlilga asoslanib, biz tenglamani tenglamani kanonik ravishda o'zgartirganda, koordinatani boshlanishi yangi nuqta S ga ko'shiriladi va eski o'qlarni omil fazosida ma'lum bir burchakka burish natijasida chiziqli hadlar yo'qoladi, erkin hadlarining qiymati o'zgaradi. Hisob - kitoblar natijasida regressiya koeffitsientlarining quyidagi qiymatlari olindi: $B_{44} = 0,40428$; $B_{55} = 1,42699$; $B_{88} = 2,21873$. Kvadratik tenglamadagi barcha koeffitsientlar ijobiy qiymatlarga ega bo'lganligi sababli, (1) tenglama bilan tavsiflangan yuzasi sirt markazining koordinatalari bo'lgan uch o'lchovli paraboloiddir: $X_{4S} = 3,0770$; $X_{5S} = 1,2289$; $X_{8S} = 1,1852$ (omillar mos ravishda quyidagi qiymatlarga ega: baraban aylanishlar chastotasi – 45,4 rad/s, materialni uzatish tezligi – 7,4.10-3 m/s, material qatlamining balandligi – 0,78 m). Shunday qilib, figura markazi tajriba maydoni va aprior tanlangan tajriba markazi yaqinida joylashganligi aniqlandi.

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